

Non-alkaloidal Constituents from *Papaver somniferum*[†]

R. S. BHAKUNI and Y. N. SHUKLA*

Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants, Lucknow-226 016

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Papaver somniferum (Papaveraceae) is an important medicinal plant containing opium alkaloids especially morphine, codeine and thebaine, possessing analgesic, antitussive and antispasmodic properties. During a large-scale preparation of an alkaloidal mixture containing about 70% morphine from unalanced capsules, it was also of interest to examine the non-alkaloidal compounds.

The air-dried unalanced capsules of *P. somniferum* (2.45 kg) were extracted with 2% AcOH in MeOH (6 × 7 dm³). The acidic MeOH extract was neutralised with NH₄OH and concentrated to dryness. The residue was treated with aqueous 2% AcOH (4 × 250 ml) and filtered. The filtrate was worked up separately for alkaloids. The residue left after acid treatment was washed with H₂O and dried under reduced pressure (27 g). A portion of it (26 g) was chromatographed over silica gel (1070 g), eluting with varying proportions of hexane, ethyl acetate and MeOH. The fractions (250 ml each) were collected and monitored by tlc. Four new compounds obtained were compound A (8 mg) eluted in hexane, compound D (70 mg) in hexane-EtOAc (96 : 4), compound F (88 mg) in hexane-EtOAc (90 : 10) and compound G (25 mg) in hexane-EtOAc (85 : 15). Compounds B, C, E and H

were identified as octacosanol, nonacosanol, β -sitosterol and β -sitosterol- β -D-glucopyranoside by comparison with authentic samples (co-tlc, ms, ¹H nmr).

Compound A has m.p. 56°; $\nu_{\max}$ 2 905, 2 850, 1 460, 1 380 (Me), 730, 715 cm⁻¹ (straight chain); M^+ at 422 corresponding to its molecular formula as C₃₀H₆₂. The generation of ion at m/z 407 (M -Me)⁺ together with the ratio of abundances of (M -Me)⁺/ (M) ⁺ indicated the compound to be branched having methyl group as a substituent¹. Mass spectrum of this compound showed that the intensity of C_nH_{2n}+1 peaks, after a maximum at $n=4$, steadily declined upto $n=26$, followed by a strong ion at $n=27$ (m/z 379). This strong ion at $n=27$ ($M-43$)⁺ suggests the attachment of a Me group at C-4². The ions at m/z 351 and 71 also agree with these assignments. These fragmentations are depicted in Fig. 1. The two terminal Me groups resonated as triplet (J 6 Hz) at δ 0.90 while the Me group at C-4 was seen as a doublet (J 6 Hz) at δ 0.80. These data lead to the structure of this compound as 4-methylnonacosane (1).

Compound D, m.p. 69°, $\nu_{\max}$ 2 950, 2 840, 1 460, 730, 720 (long-chain), 1 705 (C=O), 1 360 cm⁻¹ (Me) gave a positive 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine test for a ketone. The mass spectrum of this compound

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Fig. 1. Mass fragmentation pattern of compounds 1, 4, 6 and 7.

displayed an $(M)^+$ at m/z 366 suggesting the molecular formula as $C_{25}H_{50}O$. The presence of abundant ions at m/z 281, 253, 113, 85 (α -fission) and 296, 238, 128, 70 (β -fission) involving McLafferty rearrangement³ located the position of the carbonyl group at C-7. A double rearrangement ion at m/z 58 is characteristic for a ketone having γ -hydrogen in both alkyl fragments³. The absence of $(M-Me)^+$ indicated the straight-chain nature of this ketone. In the 1H nmr spectrum, the two methylene groups adjacent to the carbonyl function were observed as triplet (J 8 Hz) at δ 2.30. Thus the structure of this compound is assigned as 7-pentacosanone (4).

Compound F, m.p. 110° , $[\alpha]_D -3^\circ$ (c , 1, $C_{30}H_{58}N$), ν_{max} 3400, 1030 (OH), 2920, 2850, 1470, 1390 (Me), 720 cm^{-1} (long-chain) has in its mass spectrum an $(M)^+$ at m/z 422 which corresponds to $C_{30}H_{58}O$. The loss of one molecule of H_2O from

$(M)^+$ suggests it to be an alcohol. α -Fission ions at m/z 297, 267, 155 and 125 indicate the hydroxyl group at C-20. The base peak at m/z 83 supports the presence of a cyclohexane moiety at the end carbon atom⁴. The existence of cyclohexane moiety is also supported by its ^{13}C nmr spectrum which is found to be in close agreement with the related compounds⁶: δ 14.2 (C-1), 22.9 (C-2), 31.2 (C-3 to C-16), 29.8 (C-17), 28.0 (C-18), 40.7 (C-19), 75.2 (C-20), 40.7 (C-21), 29.8 (C-22), 33.9 (C-23), 34.9 (C-1'), 33.5 (C-2'), 26.5 (C-3' to C-5'), 33.5 (C-6'). In the 1H nmr spectrum, the $-CHOH$ proton was observed as multiplet at δ 3.70 (shifted to δ 4.90 in acetate). Treatment of this compound with Ac_2O /pyridine afforded a monoacetate, m.p. 93° , ν_{max} 1740, 1250 cm^{-1} , 1H nmr δ 2.00, $(M)^+$ at m/z 464 ($C_{31}H_{60}O_2$). These data lead to the structure of this compound as 20-hydroxytricosanycyclohexane (6).

NOTES

Compound G, m.p. 107°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +4^\circ(c, 1.8, \text{CHCl}_3)$, ν_{max} 3 400, 1 150, 1 060 (OH), 2 950, 2 850, 1 460, 725 (long-chain), 1 360 cm^{-1} (Me) displays in its mass spectrum an $(M)^+$ at m/z 440 ($\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_2$). The loss of two water molecules at m/z 422 and 404 from $(M)^+$ suggests it to be a diol. The prominent α -fission ions appearing at m/z 285, 255, 185, 155 located one of the hydroxyl group at C-18 whereas the second hydroxyl group is placed at the terminal position as shown by the ion m/z 409 ($M\text{-CH}_2\text{OH}^+$). In its ^1H nmr spectrum the $-\text{CHOH}$ proton appears as multiplet at 3.65 (shifted to δ 4.75 in diacetate) while $-\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ protons appear as triplet (J 6 Hz) at δ 3.45 (shifted to δ 4.11 in diacetate). When treated with Ac_2O /pyridine it yielded a diacetate, m.p. 57°, ν_{max} 1 730, 1 260 cm^{-1} , ^1H nmr δ 2.12 ($2 \times \text{OAc}$), $(M)^+$ at m/z 524 ($\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}_4$). These data suggest the structure of this compound as nonacosan-1,8-diol (7).

The straight-chain alcohols having a cyclohexane moiety are not commonly found in nature. The aliphatic alcohols are reported to play important

roles in the metabolic pathways of a number of organisms since they are capable of generating fatty acids⁶.

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